

AN ULTRASONIC MEASUREMENT OF MAGNETOSTRICTION

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Abstract – The amplitudes of shear horizontal plate waves generated by EMATs (electromagnetic acoustic transducers) are measured to obtain estimates of the magnetostriction of a steel specimen. The wave amplitude is linked to magnetostriction through an existing model that is modified in the present work to extend its applicability to a broader range of magnetic fields. Measurements with intermediate levels of EMAT currents yield estimates that best agree with strain-gage measurements of the magnetostriction.

INTRODUCTION

This work demonstrates a novel application of ultrasound: measurement of magnetostriction, the change of length of a ferromagnetic material that accompanies a change in magnetization. The technique uses noncontacting electromagnetic acoustic transducers (EMATs), which opens the possibility of using this technique to measure magnetostriction in instances where it is not practical to attach strain gages, for example, with fragile, thin films or hot plates.

Estimates of magnetostriction are obtained by measuring the amplitude of EMAT-generated plate waves. Thompson [1-3] has shown that fundamental shear horizontal (SH_0) waves can be generated magnetostrictively with the arrangement shown in Figure 1. A static magnetic field H_0 establishes an axis of tension due to magnetostriction. (In this paper, compression is regarded as a negative tension.) The ac current in

the meander coil creates an oscillating field H_ω that adds perpendicularly to the static field and, in effect, rotates the axis of tension in the surface plane, thus, creating a shear strain.

According to Thompson [1-3], the amplitude of the SH_0 wave obeys the relationship,

$$\Psi \propto \delta h \left| \frac{\partial \epsilon_{xy}}{\partial H_\omega} \right|, \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_{xy} is the magnetostrictive shear strain induced by H_0 and H_ω , h is the magnitude of H_ω at the sample surface, δ is the skin depth $\sqrt{2/(\mu_t \sigma \omega)}$, μ_t is the transverse incremental permeability, σ is the conductivity, and ω is the angular frequency. In near-saturation static fields, where the magnetization remains nearly parallel to the total magnetic field,

$$\frac{\partial \epsilon_{xy}}{\partial H_\omega} \approx \frac{3 \lambda}{2 H_0}, \quad (2)$$

Figure 1. Arrangement for magnetostrictively generating SH_0 ultrasonic waves with an EMAT.

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where λ is the magnetostriction coefficient (the longitudinal strain due to H_0).

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUE

The amplitude of propagating waves generated magnetostrictively by EMATs was measured with the arrangement shown in Figure 2. A single meander-coil EMAT was used to generate 6 mm wavelength SH_0 waves. A gated amplifier issued pulses consisting of eight cycles of sinusoids at 551 kHz, and the amplifier output was adjusted continuously to maintain a constant EMAT current. (In this paper, all currents are specified by their amplitudes.) The wave amplitude was measured with a shear piezoelectric transducer that was pressed flush against one edge of the sample with its axis of displacement aligned parallel to the plane of the sample. The amplitude of the SH_0 wave transmitted directly from the EMAT to the edge of the sample was monitored as the magnetic field was decreased from high levels.

The B-H curve and transverse incremental permeability were measured separately, and λ was measured using strain gages. Details of these measurements were reported in a previous work [4].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Measurements were performed on a 26 x 13 x 0.08 cm plate of ultralow-carbon steel that was hot- and cold-rolled and annealed. The top surface of the sample was wet-ground with 400 grit sandpaper and

Figure 2. Experimental arrangement for measuring the amplitude of SH_0 ultrasonic waves.

chemically polished with an aqueous solution of oxalic acid and hydrogen peroxide.

SH_0 wave amplitudes are shown in Figure 3 as a function of both the applied static magnetic field and the current in the transmitter EMAT. The curves have been normalized with respect to their high-field amplitudes, which rise linearly with EMAT current (in accordance with Equation (1), since h is proportional to the current). A 180° phase change occurs near the local minima of the curves between 3 and 11 kA/m.

Substitution of measurements of λ and μ into Equations (1) and (2) yields a curve that agrees well with the wave amplitudes at near-saturation fields, but, as expected, not at low fields (see Figure 3). The calculated wave amplitude can be improved somewhat by using an alternative expression for $\partial\epsilon_{xy}/\partial H_0$ that applies even when the axis of magnetostrictive tension does not rotate parallel with the magnetic field. Such an expression is calculated below under two assumptions: (1) the rotating tensile strain has the same magnitude as static tensile strain λ , and (2) the tension axis rotates parallel with the magnetization. With the tension axis oriented at angle θ with respect to the y-axis (see Figure 4), the shear strain ϵ_{xy} is

$$\epsilon_{xy} = \frac{3}{4} \lambda \sin(2\theta). \quad (3)$$

Figure 3. Normalized amplitudes of SH_0 waves generated with peak EMAT currents of 25 A (\square), 5 A (\circ), 0.5 A (Δ), and 0.1 A (\diamond). Also plotted are estimates of wave amplitudes given by Equation (1) (dashed line) and Equation (5) (solid line).

(This expression may be obtained by rotating the coordinate axes of the strain tensor for equiolumetric magnetostriction.) In the present case, θ is the rotation angle of the magnetization, which may be approximated by the rotation angle of the magnetic induction, $\arctan(\mu_t H_\omega / B_0)$ (see Figure 4). It follows that

$$\frac{\partial \varepsilon_{xy}}{\partial H_\omega} = \frac{3 \lambda}{2 H_\omega} \frac{\left(\frac{B_0}{\mu_t H_\omega} - \frac{\mu_t H_\omega}{B_0} \right)}{\left(\frac{B_0}{\mu_t H_\omega} + \frac{\mu_t H_\omega}{B_0} \right)^2}, \quad (4)$$

and, from substituting Equation (4) into Equation (1),

$$\Psi \propto \delta |\lambda| \frac{h}{H_\omega} \frac{\left| \frac{B_0}{\mu_t H_\omega} - \frac{\mu_t H_\omega}{B_0} \right|}{\left(\frac{B_0}{\mu_t H_\omega} + \frac{\mu_t H_\omega}{B_0} \right)^2}. \quad (5)$$

To estimate the wave amplitude, H_ω is taken to be the field at the skin depth, h/e . For a 6 mm wavelength meander coil with a ~ 0.1 mm liftoff, h is calculated from an available formula [3] to be 0.87 kA/m per ampere of current in the coil.

When measured values of μ_t and B_0 and an estimate of H_ω for 5 A are substituted into Equation (5), the field of the peak measured with an EMAT current of 5 A is correctly predicted, but the height of the peak is overestimated. This discrepancy is attributable to the peak lying outside the range of validity of the underlying assumptions of the derivation above. The assumptions are most valid at static fields well above the “knee” of the B-H curve,

Figure 4. Relationship between μ_t , B_0 , H_ω , and θ .

$H_{knee} (\approx 0.5 \text{ kA/m})$, where both the static and rotating magnetostrictive tensions stem from rotation of domain magnetizations. However, near H_{knee} , the first assumption is not valid, since domain wall motion is expected to contribute much more to static tension than rotating tension. At 551 kHz, domain wall motion is suppressed [5, 6], and most of the rotating tension must originate from rotation of domain magnetizations. The reduced measured peak height relative to the the calculated peak height indicates that, as the tension axis is rotated, the magnitude of the tensile strain falls below static tensile strain λ .

The drop of the relative height of the peak with decreasing EMAT currents (below 5 A) may be due to H_ω rotating domain magnetizations less effectively as H_ω decreases. When the static field is near H_{knee} , domain magnetizations are aligned close to crystalline $\langle 100 \rangle$ -type easy directions of magnetizations, and magnetic anisotropy forces oppose rotation of domain magnetizations away from these directions. On the other hand, too large an H_ω also decreases the relative height of the peak, as observed when the EMAT current is raised from 5 A to 25 A. We speculate that, as the angle of rotation is increased, the magnitude of magnetostrictive tension is reduced more, hence, leading to smaller wave amplitudes.

Figure 5 shows estimates of λ that are obtained by substituting measured wave amplitudes into the following relationship derived from Equation (5):

$$|\lambda| \propto \Psi \sqrt{\mu_t} \frac{\left(\frac{B_0}{\mu_t H_\omega} + \frac{\mu_t H_\omega}{B_0} \right)^2}{\left| \frac{B_0}{\mu_t H_\omega} - \frac{\mu_t H_\omega}{B_0} \right|}. \quad (6)$$

Different signs are assigned to results calculated from wave amplitudes above and below local minima. The local minima of the wave amplitudes give points of discontinuity in λ ; hence, calculations of λ in the neighborhood of these points are excluded in Figure 5, on the basis of being unphysical. Also, when the EMAT current is 25 A, the calculation of λ diverges at low static fields (due

to $B_0/(\mu_0 H_0)$ approaching unity), and points in the neighborhood of this divergence also are excluded from the figure.

The best estimate of the magnetostriction is obtained with data measured with an EMAT current of 5 A. While this estimate agrees with the strain-gage measurement at near-saturation fields, it is shifted below the strain-gage measurement at low fields. The reason for the discrepancy at low static fields is the same as the explanation for the discrepancy between measured and calculated wave amplitudes: at low static fields, the dynamic magnetostriction (from which the estimate is calculated) is related to static magnetostriction in a manner that is beyond the scope of the modeling in this paper. The complications stem from suppression of domain wall motion at high frequencies.

CONCLUSIONS

Measurement of the amplitude of EMAT-generated SH_0 waves provides an ultrasonic method

Figure 5. Estimates of λ derived from measurements of SH_0 wave amplitudes using peak EMAT currents of 25 A (\square), 5 A (\circ), 0.5 A (Δ), and 0.1 A (\diamond). The strain-gage measurement (solid line) is plotted for comparison purposes.

for measuring the magnetostriction of steel. It is found that measurements with intermediate levels of EMAT currents yield the best estimates of the magnetostriction. Predictions of the relative magnetostriction agree best with strain-gage measurements at near-saturation magnetic fields, and, although the calculations underestimate the maximum magnetostriction, they predict the field at which it occurs.

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